

OKR4DQ: A Case of Study for Improving Data Quality with Objectives and Key Results

Gema Gutierrez

(Rey Juan Carlos University, Madrid, Spain)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1178-8257>, gema.gutierrez@urjc.es

Moisés Rodríguez

(Castilla-La Mancha University, Ciudad Real, Spain)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2155-7409>, moises.rodriguez@uclm.es

Javier Garzás

(Rey Juan Carlos University, Madrid, Spain)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2885-5425>, javier.garzas@urjc.es

Mario Piattini

(Castilla-La Mancha University, Ciudad Real, Spain)

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7212-8279>, mario.piattini@uclm.es

Abstract: As organizations advance their digital transformation efforts, the strategic importance of data quality becomes critical. Legal and security aspects, along with the economic value of data, further emphasize the need for high-quality, reliable, and trustworthy datasets. In particular, the effectiveness of artificial intelligence techniques heavily depends on the integrity of the underlying data. However, organizations often lack structured methods to assess and improve data quality in alignment with business goals. This paper addresses this gap by introducing OKR4DQ, a methodology that leverages Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) to systematically improve data quality. The approach combines quality assessments based on the ISO/IEC 25012 standard with the definition and implementation of OKRs targeting specific quality characteristics requiring enhancement.

We present the full methodology and its application in a real-world case study, demonstrating measurable improvements in data quality and offering practical insights into the challenges and benefits of aligning data quality initiatives with business performance objectives.

Keywords: Data quality, OKR, Quality improvement

Categories: H.2.7, D.2.8, K.6.5

DOI: 10.3897/jucs.166944

1 Introduction

The increasing adoption of technologies that support Open Data practices, Big Data processing paradigms, and Business Intelligence (BI) systems has, in recent years, elevated data to the status of the most valuable asset for companies thriving in the digital era [Verdugo, 20]. Other technological advancements, such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), also depend heavily on the continuous generation and availability of large volumes of data. This data, together with the design of

groundbreaking algorithms and the increase in computing power, has led to impressive progress in different areas and industries, such as self-driving cars, virtual assistants, or the implementation of automated investment.

The importance of data quality in the digital age is a crucial issue that impacts all sectors of society and the economy. Data is at the heart of decision-making, research, strategic planning and innovation in businesses, government organizations and in our daily lives. Therefore, data quality is essential to ensure that decisions are based on accurate and reliable information.

Data quality refers, among others, to the accuracy, completeness, consistency and timeliness of the information collected and stored. A poor-quality repository can lead to erroneous decisions, lost business opportunities, compliance issues and lack of trust from customers and partners. One of the many fields where data quality is critical is the healthcare sector. Medical data errors can have serious consequences, from misdiagnosis to inappropriate treatment. For example, a widely cited 2016 study by Makary and Daniel, published in the *Journal of Patient Safety*, estimated that medical errors are the third leading cause of death in the United States, surpassing respiratory diseases [Makary, 16]. While the study does not focus solely on data issues, several analyses have pointed out that a significant portion of these errors can be attributed to inaccurate or poorly managed patient data.

To provide an overview of the status of the matter, in 2010, according to [Verdugo, 20], it was estimated that the volume of business data generated by companies will double approximately every 1.2 years. Currently, we can see that the amount of data in 2010 was 2 zettabytes and in 2023 it has risen to 120 zettabytes [Cukier, 10].

This growth and the importance that data has taken leads us to consider its importance related to the software process and the need to ensure quality in each phase of the process. However, data quality can be difficult to achieve, with problems such as data input errors, incomplete data, and inconsistent data across different channels.

In business, data quality is critical to efficient supply chain management, personalization of the customer experience and informed decision making. A study by Experian Data Quality [Experian, 23] found that 84% of companies consider data quality an important factor in achieving their strategic objectives. The data has become essential in those organizations that are transforming digitally and becoming data centric to provide an exceptional service to their stakeholders and to offer them the possibility to make the best decisions [Taylor, 22].

In addition, data quality is essential to the success of artificial intelligence and machine learning, as these systems rely on large amounts of data to train models and make automated decisions. Poor quality data can lead to inaccurate predictions and unwanted biases in the results.

In short, data quality is an invaluable asset in the digital age. It ensures the reliability of information, supports effective decision-making and promotes innovation in a variety of fields. Investing in improving data quality is essential for success and competitiveness in an increasingly information-driven world. To address these challenges, Objectives and Key Results (OKR) can be applied. OKRs are a goal management methodology that helps companies establish specific and measurable objectives and define key results to achieve them [Aiken, 17]. OKRs, although they emerged some time ago, can currently be applied as a useful tool to improve business decisions.

In this article, we hypothesize the benefit of measuring and setting objectives, applying OKRs, to improve data quality, thus improving business performance. In addition, we examine the challenges and considerations of implementing OKRs in the context of data quality, such as data governance and organizational culture. We also define a process and offer practical examples and reflections. This work aims to explore the potential of using OKRs to improve data quality. While OKRs have been extensively used in strategy execution and performance management, their application in the context of data quality remains underexplored. The following section reviews existing literature to assess the current state of research on this topic and to identify the gap that motivates the development of our proposed methodology.

2 Related Work

To position our study within the existing literature, we first review prior work on Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) and data quality management.

2.1 The use of OKRs for quality improvement

Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) constitute a strategic goal-setting framework originally developed by Andy Grove [Grove, 83] at Intel in the 1970s and later popularized by Google in the late 1990s [Doerr, 18]). Since then, OKRs have become one of the most widely adopted performance management approaches, particularly in agile and results-driven environments [Niven, 16]. At their core, OKRs are structured around two complementary elements: Objectives, which are qualitative, aspirational statements that define the intended direction, and Key Results, which are quantitative, measurable outcomes that indicate progress toward achieving the objective.

The distinctive characteristics of OKRs include: (i) their ability to promote organizational alignment; (ii) transparency, as OKRs are generally visible across the organization; (iii) an emphasis on measurement and accountability; and (iv) their iterative nature, which supports continuous improvement. Compared with traditional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which primarily serve as static measures of performance, OKRs provide a dynamic mechanism for mobilizing organizational change and adaptation.

Recent research has further examined the adoption and challenges of OKRs in different organizational contexts. Troian [Troian, 22]) conducted a systematic literature review that identifies OKRs as a results-focused management model increasingly applied across industries, while also highlighting the need for contextual adaptations. Similarly, Butler [Butler, 23]) analyzed the use of OKRs in software engineering teams, reporting benefits in terms of alignment and transparency as well as challenges in defining measurable results. These studies confirm the growing relevance of OKRs and the importance of tailoring their implementation to specific domains, which further motivates our proposal to adapt them to the field of data quality improvement.

In the context of quality improvement, OKRs can be applied by formulating clear objectives (e.g., “Improve product quality and customer satisfaction”) and defining measurable key results such as reducing defect rates, increasing customer satisfaction scores, or achieving compliance with industry-specific standards. Regular monitoring, alignment across teams, and iterative review processes ensure that quality initiatives remain on track and foster a culture of accountability and continuous improvement.

When applied to data quality, the iterative cycle inherent in OKRs becomes especially relevant: each iteration enables organizations to assess progress, identify persistent deficiencies, and redefine objectives and key results accordingly, thereby creating a continuous loop of evaluation and improvement.

Previous studies have reported the use of OKRs in managing software quality requirements [Doerr, 18], improving organizational performance [Wibawa, 21]), enhancing teaching quality in education [Sowkasem, 21], and aligning IT departments toward quality objectives [Mangipudi, 21]. However, despite these positive experiences, existing applications are fragmented and do not provide a structured integration of OKRs with recognized data quality frameworks or standards.

To address this gap, the present work proposes an adaptation of the OKR methodology specifically to the context of data quality improvement. In our approach, Objectives are defined based on deficiencies identified through formal quality assessment (e.g., ISO/IEC 25012, ISO/IEC 25024, DAMA-DMBOK). Key Results correspond to measurable quality metrics (e.g., reduce duplicate records to <5%, increase completeness by 15%). The cadence of tracking is aligned with data governance cycles, not just quarterly reviews. Organizational alignment links technical teams and business units, while iteration and learning are emphasized for continuous improvement. This iterative perspective allows successive cycles of OKRs to build on each other: in one iteration, initial goals and results are set; in the following iteration, improvements are evaluated and new, more ambitious targets are defined. The novelty of our proposal lies not in the use of OKRs per se, but in their structured integration with established data quality frameworks and standards, creating a replicable methodology. To the best of our knowledge, no previous work has provided such a validated methodology in this domain.

2.2 Data quality evaluation and improvement

The perception of data as an asset involves that organizations must commit firmly to the idea of data quality since the better their data is, the larger are the benefits they can obtain from using it [Fleckenstein, 18], [Mahanti, 19] it can be stated that data with adequate levels of quality can enable new ways to innovate in business in an increasingly competitive market [Sherman, 14].

Olson [Olson, 03], and more recently, Redman [Redman, 16] demonstrated the connection between poor data quality – Redman reported losses around 3,1 billions of USD dollars in American companies due to poor data quality-, and the increase in cost and complexity in the development of systems [Ballou, 89]. In a similar vein, [Friedman, 11], [Redman, 98], [Redman, 08], and [Laney, 17] found that there are strong relationships between low data quality and some organizational concerns:

- Poor data quality is a primary reason why 40% of all business initiatives fail to achieve their target profit.
- Data quality affects overall labour productivity by as much as 20%.
- As more business processes become automated, data quality shows itself to be the limiting factor for overall process quality.

Bearing in mind all that has been pointed out above, it is clear that organizations should invest adequate resources in the deployment of mechanisms that help to ensure the reliability of the data; that is, data that has the appropriate level of quality for its present and future use [Ladley, 12]. Establishing these mechanisms to ensure and control the quality of data is a task that must be planned with sufficient time in advance, and it needs to be carried out with clear objectives and in conformity with the organization's strategy, so that suitably skilled human resources, along with material and financial resources are allocated [Redman, 97], [Loshin, 13].

To assure and work with data quality, a large number of models, frameworks and standards have been developed in recent years. Within these proposals, two dimensions can be distinguished. On the one hand, the work related to the quality of processes for data governance, management and quality, among which the following can be highlighted: DMM, DAMA [DAMA, 17], ISO 8000 [ISO, 16], MAMD [Caballero, 23] and more recently the UNE technical specifications [UNE, 23]. All these proposals, with their similarities and differences, are based on the premise that companies that have quality processes for working with their data will have quality assets from which to make decisions.

Several methodologies have also emerged to operationalize data quality evaluation based on established standards. Notably, Guerra- García [Guerra-García, 23] proposed a structured methodology grounded in ISO/IEC 25012 to define and manage data quality requirements throughout the software development lifecycle, with the goal of achieving "Data Quality by Design". Their approach emphasizes early integration of DQ into system requirements and development activities. While these contributions address data quality from a design-time perspective, our work focuses on post-deployment improvement, combining ISO/IEC 25012-based evaluation with strategic alignment mechanisms via OKRs. Thus, the proposed methodology complements existing approaches by providing a structured framework for defining and tracking improvement goals once data quality issues have been identified in existing systems.

On the other hand, there is the dimension of the quality of the data product itself, i.e. the quality of the data that is stored in a particular repository. In this article we will focus on this dimension of data quality.

Considering our experience in the field of industrial assessment and certification of software and data quality [Verdugo, 24], as defined in [Gualo, 21], three fundamental elements are necessary to be able to evaluate the quality of the data in a repository: a quality model with the quality characteristics to be evaluated, an evaluation process with the activities to be followed to carry out the evaluation and a tool that supports the measurement and evaluation process in a way that is as automated and repeatable as possible. For each of these elements, the AQCLab laboratory (first accredited for data quality assessments) developed an environment consisting of:

- A data quality model based on ISO/IEC 25012 [ISO/IEC, 08] and ISO/IEC 25024 [ISO/IEC, 15], which includes the data quality characteristics (Figure 1), as well as the underlying properties, measures and thresholds.
- A data quality evaluation and certification process based on ISO/IEC 25040 [ISO/IEC, 11] which defines the activities, tasks, inputs, outputs and roles necessary to carry out a data quality evaluation.

- A semi-automatic environment for data quality evaluation based on query tools and in-house software that generate evaluation results in accordance with the defined model and measures.

Figure 1: AQCLab Data Quality Model [Gualo, 21]

Furthermore, in order to evaluate the data stored in a repository and determine its quality, it is first necessary to identify the data quality requirements, also known as business rules, that the data must meet. To do this, there are models and methodologies such as the one described in BR4DQ [Caballero, 22], which presents a set of activities necessary to identify, define, and validate the quality requirements that the data must meet in order to be valid and useful for the business.

Once the quality rules that the data must meet have been defined together with the business people, these rules are converted into queries, using the specific language needed to work with the data repository where they are stored. By executing these queries, it is possible to know the amount of data that does not comply with the defined quality rules and, using the quality model defined in [Gualo, 21], it is possible to obtain the quality value of the data repository. In this case, two situations may broadly occur:

1. The data meets the necessary quality levels, i.e., the proportion of data that does not comply according to the evaluation and certification model defined in [Gualo, 21] is minimal and therefore the quality of the repository can be certified.

2. The data does not meet the required quality level, i.e., the proportion of data that fails to comply with the defined quality rules exceeds the permitted thresholds and therefore a data cleansing process is necessary. To do this, depending on which rules have been breached (unnecessary data redundancy, completeness issues, outdated data, etc.), the organization that owns the data must identify each of the cases detected and determine the best way to resolve the breach. To this end, over the years, cleaning,

elimination, standardization, normalization, or enrichment processes have been used to correct or improve data quality.

Beyond the detection of data quality problems, the literature on data cleaning focuses on methods and systems aimed at repairing data so that datasets comply with defined quality requirements and constraints. The foundational literature on data cleaning begins with the synthesis of problems and approaches by [Rahm, 00] and evolves toward interactive data transformation and cleaning systems such as [Raman, 01]. In parallel, a highly influential line of work formalizes data cleaning and repair based on constraints (e.g., dependencies), highlighting Conditional Functional Dependencies for the detection of inconsistencies and for guiding repair actions [Bohannon, 07], together with cost models to handle inconsistencies through value modifications [Bohannon, 05]. A modern and widely cited overview of the field—covering detection taxonomies, qualitative repairing, scalability challenges, and emerging interfaces—is presented in the tutorial by [Chu, 16].

In data repair in the strict sense (i.e., restoring consistency under well-defined semantics), the database repairing and consistent query answering (CQA) frameworks are fundamental. These are systematized in the monograph by [Bertossi, 11] and in his survey of CQA [Bertossi, 06], with a historical review and recent research directions discussed in [Bertossi, 19]. Finally, automatic and semi-automatic repair approaches have increasingly incorporated interaction and learning: Guided Data Repair integrates user feedback to prioritize updates [Yakout, 11]; SCAREd models repairs as likelihood maximization under bounded changes [Yakout, 13]; HoloClean proposes holistic repairs by combining constraints, external signals, and statistical reasoning through probabilistic inference [Rekatsinas, 17]; and ActiveClean links data cleaning and learning by prioritizing cleaning actions based on their impact on machine learning models [Krishnan, 16].

2.3 Comparison with Existing Data Quality Improvement Approaches

Several existing methodologies have been developed to address data quality improvement, ranging from rule-based frameworks such as BR4DQ (Business Rules for Data Quality) [Caballero, 22], which focuses on defining and validating business rules for data, to technical approaches like data cleansing, enrichment, standardization, and data profiling. These methods typically emphasize correction and validation activities, often relying on technical tools to detect and fix data anomalies.

However, these approaches generally lack a systematic mechanism for aligning improvement efforts with organizational strategy, and they do not provide structured follow-up on whether improvements are progressing toward specific business goals. In contrast, OKR4DQ introduces a novel perspective by integrating the ISO/IEC 25012-based quality assessment with the OKR (Objectives and Key Results) methodology. This enables organizations not only to identify which data quality characteristics are deficient, but also to define clear, measurable, and business-aligned objectives for improvement, with periodic tracking and organizational visibility.

Unlike rule-based or tool-specific methodologies, OKR4DQ positions data quality improvement as a continuous, goal-driven process, fostering alignment across departments and encouraging accountability and transparency. To our knowledge, no

previous proposal has combined a recognized data quality standard with a strategic management framework in this way.

Aspect	Traditional DQ Improvement (e.g., Cleansing, BR4DQ)	OKR4DQ (Proposed Approach)
Primary Focus	Data correction, rule enforcement	Strategic alignment and goal-driven improvement
Underlying Standard	Ad hoc or BR4DQ (rules); some use of ISO standards	ISO/IEC 25012-based quality model
Improvement Mechanism	Technical interventions (cleansing, standardization)	OKRs defined per DQ characteristic to guide improvement
Business Alignment	Indirect or limited	Central: OKRs align with organizational strategy
Measurement and Tracking	Often tool-based or manual	Key Results tracked regularly using OKR framework
Organizational Visibility	Typically confined to data teams	Transparent across departments and stakeholders
Adaptability over time	Static unless manually revised	Iterative and flexible; objectives evolve as needed
Accountability and Ownership	Implicit or unclear	Explicit through OKRs and team responsibilities
Use Case Orientation	Reactive, focused on existing data problems	Proactive, enables continuous improvement cycle

Table 1: Comparison between methodologies for Data Quality

3 Description of OKR4DQ: Methodology for applying OKR to Data Quality

The OKR4DQ methodology is designed to support continuous data quality improvement by integrating quality assessment standards with strategic goal-setting practices. It combines the evaluation model defined by ISO/IEC 25012 with the OKRs framework to create an iterative process that identifies, prioritizes, and addresses data quality deficiencies through measurable and business-aligned improvement goals. This section details the six-step process that structures the methodology, ensuring that improvements are tracked, evaluated, and adjusted over time. Each step builds upon the previous, enabling organizations to replicate the approach systematically and adapt it to various domains.

The process for iteratively improving data quality, encompassing six key steps:

1. Scope definition and dataset selection: The first step involves defining the scope of the quality improvement effort by identifying the target dataset or repository. This selection is informed by business priorities or previously observed data quality issues. The purpose is not to discover data to analyze,

but to focus the improvement effort on a dataset whose quality is critical for operational, analytical, or strategic purposes.

2. **First Data evaluation** Following the selection process, an initial evaluation of the chosen data sets is conducted to establish a baseline understanding of their quality. This evaluation serves as a crucial benchmark, providing insight into the current state of data integrity, completeness, and accuracy. The quality evaluation is based on the ISO/IEC 25012 data quality model, which defines fifteen quality characteristics, including completeness, accuracy, consistency, and timeliness, among others. The measurements used in this methodology follow the ISO/IEC 25024 standard for data quality measurement, and results are recorded to establish a baseline for comparison in future iterations.
3. **First study of the results.** Upon completing the initial data evaluation, the obtained results are meticulously analyzed and summarized. This analysis involves identifying areas of strength as well as pinpointing potential weaknesses or deficiencies in the data. Through collaborative discussions, stakeholders deliberate on possible avenues for improvement.
4. **Definition and implementation of OKRs:** Building upon the insights gleaned from the initial evaluation and discussions, based on the deficiencies identified in the previous steps, specific OKRs are defined following the Doerr's methodology [Doerr, 18] to target improvement of selected data quality characteristics (e.g., reduce null values in key fields by 50% within Q3). Each OKR links a clear objective with 2–4 measurable key results, following the SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound). These OKRs are then implemented at the relevant organizational level, with assigned responsibilities, timelines, and tracking mechanisms. These OKRs serve as actionable goals, outlining specific objectives and measurable outcomes aimed at enhancing data quality. Once defined, the OKRs are implemented across the organization, guiding targeted efforts to improve data integrity and reliability.
5. **Second data evaluation:** After the implementation of OKRs, a second round of data evaluation is conducted using the same criteria as the initial assessment. This iterative approach allows organizations to assess the impact of the implemented OKRs on data quality. By comparing the results of the second evaluation to the baseline established in the first iteration, organizations can gauge the effectiveness of their improvement efforts.
6. **Analysis of the results:** Finally, the results of the second data evaluation are thoroughly analyzed and interpreted. Any observed improvements in data quality are summarized and presented, highlighting areas of progress and success. Additionally, stakeholders engage in in-depth discussions to identify lessons learned, potential challenges, and opportunities for further enhancement. Importantly, the workflow is designed to be iterative rather than linear. Steps such as defining OKRs, implementing them, and conducting

evaluations (Steps 4–6) are executed periodically or whenever relevant changes occur in the underlying data. This ensures that the process remains responsive and continuously aligned with evolving data conditions and organizational needs. Through this continuous feedback loop, organizations can refine their data quality improvement strategies, respond promptly to new challenges, and drive ongoing improvements over time. In essence, this structured and iterative approach provides organizations with a systematic framework for enhancing data quality. By leveraging data-driven insights, setting clear objectives, and implementing targeted interventions, organizations can foster a culture of data excellence and unlock the full potential of their data assets. Figure 2.1 and 2.2 illustrates the process.

The methodology is intended to be replicable across organizations and domains, provided that quality measurements can be operationalized, and improvement targets can be defined. For this reason, each step includes clearly defined roles (e.g., data stewards, analysts, business owners), required inputs (e.g., repository metadata, quality metrics), and expected outputs (e.g., OKR definitions, evaluation reports). A detailed template for the evaluation and OKR definition process is presented in the case study section.

Figure 2.1: Process for iteratively improving data quality, encompassing the three firsts' steps

Figure 2.2: Process for iteratively improving data quality, encompassing the three last step

4 Case of Study

This case study was conducted in the context of evaluating data quality in a repository derived from industry surveys about professionals' experience with scaled agile frameworks. The case focuses on evaluating and improving five key ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics (Accuracy, Completeness, Consistency, Credibility, Timeliness) through the OKR4DQ methodology.

The design of the study follows the guidelines provided for case study research in [Yin, 09]. We followed the case study protocol according to [Brereton, 08]. Robson [Robson, 02], Yin [Yin, 09] and Benbasat [Benbasat, 87] provide definitions of case study research. Among them they state that a case study can be applied as a comparative research strategy, comparing the results of using one method or some form of manipulation with the results of using another approach. [Wohlin, 12] also states that it is used to avoid bias and ensure internal validity, and that it is necessary to create a solid basis for evaluating the results of the case study. Furthermore, in [Kitchenham, 95] propose three ways of organizing the study to facilitate the study.

This study aimed at answering the following research questions:

RQ1: The introduction and adoption of Objectives and Key Results (OKR) may have a positive impact on enhancing data quality, as compared to scenarios where OKRs are not employed.

RQ2: Aligning organizational objectives with measurable results can potentially contribute to improved data integrity and reliability.

4.1 First Iteration

The first iteration of the OKR4DQ methodology begins with the selection and evaluation of the dataset to be analyzed. The selected dataset consists of structured survey responses collected from 149 professionals and managers in the software development sector. The survey focuses on assessing their knowledge, experience, and adoption of scaled agile frameworks and best practices.

A stable copy of the production database was used to ensure data consistency throughout the evaluation process. This dataset was chosen due to its strategic relevance for understanding the maturity and adoption of agile practices in the industry, and because previous exploratory analyses indicated potential data quality issues.

Data Quality Evaluation – First Iteration

The data quality evaluation followed the ISO/IEC 25012 standard, focusing on five key characteristics: Accuracy, Completeness, Consistency, Credibility, and Timeliness. For each characteristic, a set of quality properties (e.g., Syntactic Accuracy, Record Completeness, Referential Integrity) was assessed using guidelines and measurement rules derived from ISO/IEC 25024.

The evaluation process consisted of the following structured steps:

- Definition of Purpose: Clarify the goals of the data evaluation and determine the relevant data product quality requirements.

- Specification of Evaluation: Select the quality measures, define decision criteria for each measure, and establish overall thresholds for quality assessment.
- Design of Evaluation Activities: Plan the sequence of tasks, roles, and tools required to perform the assessment.
- Execution: Apply measurement queries to the dataset to obtain values for each property, calculate quality scores, and identify strengths and weaknesses.
- Reporting and Review: Generate a summary report including quality scores and suggested improvement areas, and review findings with data owners.

Scoring Methodology

Each quality characteristic was scored on a 1-to-5 scale, where:

1 = very poor quality,

5 = excellent quality.

The scores were derived from measurable indicators using predefined thresholds. For example:

Accuracy: measured by the percentage of syntactically and semantically valid values.

1: <60%, 2: 60–70%, 3: 70–85%, 4: 85–95%, 5: ≥95%

Completeness: measured by the percentage of non-null values in critical fields.

1: <50%, 2: 50–65%, ..., 5: ≥95%

Thresholds for all characteristics were defined jointly by the research team and domain experts from the organization, using industry benchmarks and internal business requirements. This quantification process ensured that results are replicable, comparable across iterations, and interpretable for quality improvement actions.

Result of the evaluation

The results obtained in the data quality assessment for the survey database are presented below. The analysis begins with general quality characteristics (as defined in ISO/IEC 25012) and is then expanded into more specific quality properties. Each characteristic is assessed on a 1-to-5 scale, where 1 represents poor quality and 5 represents excellent quality, based on quantitative thresholds derived from predefined metrics (e.g., % of null values, rule violations).

The scores obtained for each characteristic in the first evaluation were:

- Accuracy (EXAC): 1
- Completeness (COMP): 2
- Consistency (CONS): 2
- Credibility (CRED): 2
- Timeliness (ACT): 2

These results are visualized in Figure 3, which shows a radar chart of the evaluated characteristics. The acronyms used in the figure represent the following dimensions of data quality:

EXAC = Accuracy: Degree to which data correctly represents the real-world values it is intended to model.

COMP = Completeness: Extent to which required data is present in the dataset (e.g., no missing values in critical fields).

CONS = Consistency: Absence of contradictions within the dataset (e.g., coherent formatting, no duplicate identifiers).

CRED = Credibility: Degree to which data is regarded as trustworthy and believable.

ACT = Timeliness: Degree to which data is up-to-date and available when needed.

As shown, Accuracy was the most critical issue, scoring the lowest, while the other four characteristics also showed significant room for improvement. These findings guided the definition of OKRs in the subsequent iteration, aiming to address the specific weaknesses identified in this baseline assessment.

Figure 3: Radar chart of pre-OKR evaluation results for ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics: EXAC = Accuracy, COMP = Completeness, CONS = Consistency, CRED = Credibility, ACT = Timeliness. Values range from 1 (low quality) to 5 (high quality)

The detailed data quality evaluation includes a set of quality properties derived from the ISO/IEC 25024 measurement framework, corresponding to the five main ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics assessed previously. Each property was measured using specific rules and thresholds, and results are presented as percentages ranging from 0% (very poor quality) to 100% (excellent quality).

Figure 4 displays a bar chart summarizing the results obtained for each property. The acronyms used in the figure represent the following data quality properties:

EXAC_SINT = Syntactic Accuracy: Compliance of values with the defined syntactic format (e.g., date format, decimal notation).

RAN_EXAC = Range Accuracy: Proportion of values within the expected domain (e.g., valid score ranges).

EXAC_SEMAN = Semantic Accuracy: Degree to which values are semantically valid in their business context.

COMP_REG = Record Completeness: Presence of values in required fields for each record.

COMP_FICH = File Completeness: Compliance with expected number of records per entity.

COMP_VAL_ESP = Expected Value Completeness: Presence of expected distinct values within categorical fields.

FAL_COMP_FICH = False File Completeness: Detection of duplicate or invalid records based on entity-specific rules.

INT_REF = Referential Integrity: Validity of foreign key references across entities.

RIES_INCO = Inconsistency Risk: Presence or absence of duplicate or conflicting records.

CONS_SEMAN = Semantic Consistency: Coherence between related attribute values (e.g., job title matching department).

CONS_FORM = Format Consistency: Uniformity in format across fields with the same data type or function.

CRED_FUEN = Source Credibility: Trustworthiness of the data source (e.g., verified origin).

CRED_VAL_DAT = Data Value Credibility: Validity of attribute values based on known reliable patterns or sources.

FREC_ACT = Update Frequency: Timeliness of data updates based on expected refresh cycles.

CONV_ACT = Update Convenience: Suitability of update processes for practical use (e.g., maintaining most recent valid record).

As seen in the figure 4, properties such as File Completeness, Expected Value Completeness, Referential Integrity, Semantic Consistency, and Source Credibility achieved high scores, indicating strong reliability in those dimensions. However, others such as Syntactic Accuracy, Range Accuracy, Semantic Accuracy, and Update Convenience revealed significant weaknesses.

These weaknesses included missing syntactic validation rules, values falling outside expected ranges, semantic mismatches, and issues with survey participants being able to submit multiple conflicting responses. Such findings served as the basis for defining targeted OKRs in the second iteration, with the aim of improving these specific areas of the dataset.

Figure 4: Bar chart of quality scores by property. Acronyms represent detailed properties defined in ISO/IEC 25024. Scores are shown as percentages from 0 to 100%.

4.2 Second Iteration

Definition and Implementation of OKRs

Following the initial data quality evaluation, a set of Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) was defined collaboratively by the research team and the data owners—specifically, a group of managers responsible for the survey repository. These OKRs were intended to guide targeted improvements in those ISO/IEC 25012 data quality characteristics that had received low scores in the first iteration (e.g., Accuracy, Completeness, Consistency, Credibility, Timeliness).

The formulation of OKRs followed the methodology proposed by [Doerr, 18], where each OKR is composed of a qualitative objective and one or more quantitative key results. To adapt the OKR framework to the domain of data quality improvement, we aligned each objective with a specific characteristic of data quality, and defined key results based on the same metrics and measurement techniques used during the initial assessment (e.g., % of null values, referential integrity rate, syntactic format compliance).

Formulation Process

The definition of each OKR followed a structured two-part process: first, defining the Objective, and second, specifying the corresponding Key Results.

Objective (O): A high-level, qualitative goal describing the intended improvement to a specific DQ characteristic. Objectives were required to:

- Be aligned with overall data governance priorities.
- Be clear and actionable.

• Represent a meaningful and challenging improvement.
 Key Results (KR): Quantitative indicators of progress toward the objective. Each KR was required to:

- Be based on a clear metric (e.g., percentage of valid entries, number of duplicate records).
- Include a specific target value and timeframe.
- Enable objective verification of achievement.

For instance, for the characteristic of completeness, an OKR might be:

Objective: Ensure the completeness of critical survey responses.

Key Result: Reduce the number of incomplete records by at least 50% within one month.

Implementation Strategy

Once defined, the OKRs were incorporated into the organization's data governance and quality assurance workflows. The implementation involved the establishment of clear operational rules for how OKRs would be monitored and validated. These included:

- Assigning ownership of each objective to a responsible team.
- Establishing time-bound goals and tracking mechanisms.
- Ensuring alignment between OKRs and broader business needs.

To evaluate effectiveness, a second survey was conducted to a 149 professionals and managers in the software development sector, identical in structure to the first, and the same data quality evaluation process was applied to the new dataset. The follow-up assessment allowed us to directly compare pre- and post-intervention quality scores and determine the degree to which OKRs led to measurable improvements.

Examples of Data Quality OKRs

To illustrate the application of the methodology, the following examples show how OKRs were designed for each of the five ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics:

Accuracy (EXAC)

Objective: Improve the accuracy of survey respondent contact data.

Key Result: Increase the syntactic and semantic accuracy rate from 60% to at least 90%.

Completeness (COMP)

Objective: Ensure completeness of mandatory survey fields.

Key Result: Achieve 95% completion rate across all critical fields.

Consistency (CONS)

Objective: Eliminate inconsistencies between related data entries.

Key Result: Reduce inter-record inconsistencies to zero.

Credibility (CRED)

Objective: Enhance the credibility of respondent-reported values.

Key Result: Verify 90% of responses using cross-validation rules or external sources.

Timeliness (ACT)

Objective: Improve update frequency and recency of the data.

Key Result: Ensure data updates occur within one week of collection in 100% of cases.

Second data quality evaluation

Following the definition and implementation of OKRs, a new round of data collection was conducted using the same survey instrument as in the first iteration. The aim was to evaluate whether the application of OKRs had a measurable impact on improving the quality of the survey data.

The data quality assessment was repeated using the same methodology and measurement framework as in the first evaluation. This ensured comparability and consistency across iterations. As before, the assessment was based on five key characteristics defined in ISO/IEC 25012: Accuracy (EXAC), Completeness (COMP), Consistency (CONS), Credibility (CRED), and Timeliness (ACT).

The results obtained in this second evaluation show a clear improvement across all five characteristics. The radar chart in Figure 5 illustrates the post-OKR scores across these characteristics. As shown in the chart, all characteristics showed notable improvement, with Completeness, Consistency, and Credibility reaching the maximum score of 5. These results suggest that the OKRs effectively targeted the deficiencies observed in the first iteration and that the actions derived from them led to tangible improvements in the quality of the dataset.

Figure 5: Radar chart of post-OKR evaluation results for ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics: EXAC = Accuracy, COMP = Completeness, CONS = Consistency, CRED = Credibility, ACT = Timeliness. Values range from 1 (low quality) to 5 (high quality).

Detailed Property Evaluation

To complement the global analysis of characteristics, a property-level evaluation was also conducted. This finer-grained assessment includes specific data quality properties aligned with ISO/IEC 25024, such as Syntactic Accuracy, Record Completeness, Referential Integrity, and others.

Figure 6 presents the scores for each property, measured as percentages of compliance or correctness. The following properties achieved high-quality values (close to or at 100%):

- Syntactic Accuracy (EXAC_SINT): Valid syntactic formatting across fields
- Semantic Accuracy (EXAC_SEMAN): Semantic correctness of values within their context
- Record Completeness (COMP_REG): Absence of null values in required fields
- File Completeness (COMP_FICH): Correct number of records per entity
- Expected Value Completeness (COMP_VAL_ESP): Inclusion of expected distinct values
- False File Completeness (FAL_COMP_FICH): Absence of duplicate or redundant entries
- Referential Integrity (INT_REF): Valid foreign key relationships
- Format Consistency (CONS_FORM): Consistent formatting across similar fields
- Semantic Consistency (CONS_SEMAN): Coherence among logically related attributes
- Inconsistency Risk (RIES_INCO): Low risk of contradictions or duplicates
- Source Credibility (CRED_FUEN): Trustworthiness of the data source
- Data Value Credibility (CRED_VAL_DAT): Reasonable and verifiable values
- Update Frequency (FREC_ACT): Timeliness of data updates
- Update Convenience (CONV_ACT): Practical adequacy of the update mechanism

Figure 6: Bar chart of quality scores by property. Acronyms represent detailed properties defined in ISO/IEC 25024. Scores are shown as percentages from 0 to 100%.

These results demonstrate that the OKR4DQ methodology effectively enabled targeted and measurable improvements in data quality, confirming its value as a structured framework for continuous improvement based on standards and business alignment.

4.3 Analysis of the results

In order to do a comparative analysis, Figures 7 and 8 present scatter plots displaying the evolution of scores for each characteristic and property. Each pair of points shows the first and second evaluation values side by side. In all cases, upward trends were observed, confirming the positive effect of the OKR4DQ methodology.

Figure 7: Results of the detail characteristics

Each characteristic, including Accuracy, Completeness, Consistency, Credibility, and Timeliness, is plotted along the x-axis, representing key dimensions of data quality. The y-axis denotes the Evaluation Result, reflecting the score or rating assigned to each characteristic during the evaluations. Observing figure 7, we note that for some characteristics, such as Accuracy and Consistency, the scores remain relatively stable between the first and second evaluations, indicated by the proximity of the blue and green data points. This suggests that these aspects of data quality have remained consistent or have seen minimal changes over the course of the evaluations. Conversely, for other characteristics, such as Completeness and Timeliness, we observe noticeable improvements in scores between the first and second evaluations. The green data points appear higher on the y-axis compared to their corresponding blue data points, indicating an enhancement in these aspects of data quality following the implementation of corrective measures or interventions.

The figure provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of data quality improvement efforts over time. By visually comparing scores across different characteristics and iterations, organizations can identify areas of strength and weakness, track progress, and make informed decisions to further enhance data quality and integrity.

It can be seen in the figure that in the first evaluation the results of the characteristics are low and in the second evaluation the results are better and higher in all characteristics.

Similar to the characteristics, to compare the properties we use the scatter plot, figure 8 to see the comparison of the first evaluation and the second evaluation.

The graph provides a visual representation of evaluation results across different properties, with data points indicating the scores obtained during the first and second evaluations. By analyzing the key aspects of the graph, we can see that, each property, such as “compfich”, “reg,” “valsp,” and others, is listed along the x-axis, representing specific characteristics or attributes under evaluation. These properties likely correspond to different aspects of data quality or performance metrics within a given system or dataset.

The y-axis denotes the Evaluation Result, representing the score or rating assigned to each property during the evaluations. The scale ranges from 0 to 100, indicating the range of possible scores.

The blue data points correspond to the scores obtained during the First Evaluation, while the green data points represent the scores from the Second Evaluation. By comparing the positions of these data points for each property, we can discern trends and patterns in how evaluation results have evolved over time. The characteristics in the first evaluation that seemed to not be evaluated had a value of 100 in the first evaluation.

Figure 8: Results of the detail characteristics

We can identify properties where there has been a noticeable improvement between the first and second evaluations. In these cases, the green data points appear higher on the y-axis compared to their corresponding blue data points, indicating an enhancement in performance or quality.

Overall, the graph offers valuable insights into the effectiveness of improvement efforts and the evolution of performance across different properties.

The application of OKR4DQ allowed the organization to identify, monitor, and improve specific weaknesses in data quality with clear alignment to business goals. This structured approach helped data owners and stakeholders engage in the improvement process actively. From a research perspective, this study demonstrates the feasibility of integrating ISO-based DQ assessments with strategic goal-setting, offering a replicable model for data-driven organizations. Future work may include applying the method in other domains and automating OKR formulation based on quality metrics.

Review

Finally, it is necessary to review the results obtained and identify possible refinements to the process. This is the proposed methodology to evaluate the data quality of a data repository and improve the indicators with the use of OKRs.

We have engaged in discussions with the business, referring to the owners of the database, and they have indeed confirmed that the data they are currently working with, regardless of its quality assessment, is significantly more comprehensive and clearer for their utilization. As a result, they have been able to undertake a myriad of actions, leveraging the enhanced clarity and completeness of the data.

In terms of threads to validity we can say that it would be interesting to be able to implement the use case with the same database to facilitate the process and to verify that the same positive results are obtained.

5 Discussion

Ensuring high-quality data is a pressing challenge in modern organizations, especially as they increasingly depend on data-driven decision-making. Although multiple standards and frameworks, such as ISO/IEC 25012, ISO/IEC 25024, and DAMA, offer guidance for evaluating and managing data quality, they primarily emphasize assessment rather than strategic improvement. This limits their capacity to align data quality efforts with business objectives and organizational priorities.

In response to this gap, this paper proposed OKR4DQ, a methodology that integrates Objectives and Key Results (OKRs), a goal-setting framework widely used in management, into the data quality improvement process. OKR4DQ operationalizes the improvement cycle by linking ISO-based measurement (ISO/IEC 25012 characteristics and ISO/IEC 25024 metrics) with actionable objectives and quantifiable outcomes.

The methodology was applied to a real-world case study involving survey data on agile management practices. Results demonstrate substantial improvement across all assessed data quality characteristics. As shown in section 4, initial evaluation scores ranged from 1 (poor) to 2 (low-moderate) across key characteristics such as accuracy (EXAC), completeness (COMP), consistency (CONS), credibility (CRED), and timeliness (ACT). After implementing the OKRs, a second evaluation yielded scores between 4 and 5 across all dimensions (Figure 5), reflecting significant quality gains.

As illustrated in Figure 8, numerous properties, such as Syntactic Accuracy (EXAC_SINT), Range Accuracy (RAN_EXAC), and Update Convenience (CONV_ACT), initially received near-zero evaluation scores. After the intervention, these properties reached 100%, indicating full compliance with defined quality rules. This quantitative jump underscores the effectiveness of the OKR4DQ cycle, particularly in transforming critical areas that were previously deficient.

These improvements were not achieved through technical changes in the data infrastructure or collection system, but rather through process-based interventions: rule adjustments, stakeholder alignment, and prioritization driven by OKRs. This reinforces the idea that organizational alignment and goal-setting can lead to measurable data quality gains, even in the absence of system overhauls.

Compared to existing methodologies, such as the Data Management Maturity Model (DMM) or BR4DQ, which emphasize governance structures or business rules, OKR4DQ offers a more lightweight and flexible solution. Its use of OKRs promotes accountability, iterative progress, and cross-team alignment, addressing common challenges such as stakeholder disengagement and difficulty sustaining long-term quality initiatives.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the case study was limited to a single dataset within one organizational context. While the dataset includes 149 records, the generalizability of findings to other domains remains to be tested. Second, although ISO standards guided metric selection, the thresholds used to assign scores (e.g., 1-5 scale for completeness or accuracy) were context-specific, agreed upon by domain experts and data owners. Lastly, while the involvement of stakeholders in defining OKRs improved engagement and relevance, it also introduced subjectivity that could vary across applications.

Future work will focus on extending the use of OKR4DQ to other domains (e.g., healthcare, finance, logistics) and data types (e.g., transactional data, time series, sensor data). It will also explore the integration of emerging technologies, such as machine learning to assist in the automatic detection of quality issues and tracking progress toward OKRs. It is also important to acknowledge that, while the evaluation has been conducted on a relatively small dataset representative of real-world conditions, further validation should be performed on larger datasets comprising thousands or even millions of records to ensure scalability and generalizability of the results.

In conclusion, OKR4DQ contributes to bridging the gap between technical data quality assessment and strategic organizational action. The positive outcomes of the case study support the methodology's practical utility and show that structured, goal-oriented improvement cycles can lead to meaningful and measurable enhancements in data quality. By aligning data quality improvements with strategic objectives, OKR4DQ empowers organizations to better leverage their data assets in support of reliable, informed decision-making.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported and it is part of the actions of the AQCLab, laboratory for the Evaluation of Software Product Quality and Data Quality. ANDANTE Project (Ref. SBPLY/24/180225/000039) funded with the support of the UE through the FEDER and the JCCM, and the "Agencia de Investigación e Innovación de CLM".

SINERGIA (2025-GRIN-38310), financial support for the execution of applied research projects, within the framework of the UCLM Own Research Plan, 85% co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund (FEDER).

Proyecto RiskIA (Ref. 3930718/2025) funded with the support of the UE through the FEDER and the JCCM, and the "Programa de apoyo a la innovación: Innova-Adelante".

References

- [Aiken, 17] Aiken, P., Harbour, T. Data Strategy and the Enterprise Data Executive. Technics Publications, USA, 2017.
- [Ballou, 89] Ballou, D. P., Tayi, G. K. Methodology for Allocating Resources for Data Quality Enhancement. Communications of the ACM, 32(3), 320–329, 1989.
- [Benbasat, 87] Benbasat, I., Goldstein, D. K., Mead, M. The Case Research Strategy in Studies of Information Systems. MIS Quarterly, 1987.
- [Bereton, 08] Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B. A., Budgen, D. Using a Protocol Template for Case Study Planning. In: Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE), 2008.
- [Bertossi, 11] Bertossi, L. E. Database Repairing and Consistent Query Answering. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2011.
- [Bertossi, 06] Bertossi, L. Consistent Query Answering in Databases. ACM SIGMOD Record, 35(2), 68–76, 2006.

- [Bertossi, 19] Bertossi, L. E. Database Repairs and Consistent Query Answering: Origins and Developments. In: PODS 2019, 48–58.
- [Bohannon, 05] Bohannon, P., Flaster, M., Fan, W., Rastogi, R. A Cost-Based Model for Repairing Constraints. In: SIGMOD 2005, 143–154.
- [Bohannon, 07] Bohannon, P., Fan, W., Geerts, F., Jia, X., Kementsietsidis, A. Conditional Functional Dependencies for Data Cleaning. In: ICDE 2007, 746–755.
- [Butler, 23] Butler, S., Zimmermann, T., Bird, C. Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) in Software Engineering Teams: Benefits and Challenges. arXiv preprint, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.00236>
- [Caballero, 22] Caballero, I., Gualo, F., Rodríguez, M., Piattini, M. BR4DQ: A Methodology for Grouping Business Rules for Data Quality Evaluation. Information Systems, 2022.
- [Caballero, 23] Caballero, I., Piattini, M. Data Governance: From the Fundamentals to Real Cases. Springer, Cham, 2023.
- [Chu, 16] Chu, X., Ilyas, I. F., Krishnan, S., Wang, J. Data Cleaning: Overview and Emerging Challenges. In: SIGMOD 2016, 2201–2206.
- [Cukier, 10] Cukier, K. Data, data everywhere: A special report on managing information. The Economist, 2010.
- [DAMA, 17] DAMA-DMBOK: Data Management Body of Knowledge, 2nd ed. Technics Publications, Basking Ridge, NJ, 2017.
- [Doerr, 18] Doerr, J. Measure What Matters: How Google, Bono, and the Gates Foundation Rock the World with OKRs. Harvard Business Review Press, Boston, MA, 2018.
- [Experian, 23] Experian Data Quality. The consequences of poor data quality for a business. Experian Blog, 2023.
- [Fleckenstein, 18] Fleckenstein, M., Fellows, L. Modern Data Strategy. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018.
- [Friedman, 11] Friedman, T., Smith, M. Measuring the Business Value of Data Quality. Gartner, Stamford, CT, 2011.
- [Grove, 83] Grove, A. S. High Output Management. Random House, 1983.
- [Gualo, 21] Gualo, F., Rodríguez, M., Verdugo, J., Caballero, I., Piattini, M. Data Quality Certification Using ISO/IEC 25012: Industrial Experiences. Journal of Systems and Software, 2021.
- [Guerra-García, 23] Guerra-García, C., Nikiforova, A., Jiménez, S., Pérez-González, H. G., Ramírez-Torres, M., Ontañón-García, L. ISO/IEC 25012-based methodology for managing data quality requirements. Data & Knowledge Engineering, 145, 102152, 2023.
- [ISO/IEC, 08] ISO/IEC 25012: Software Engineering — Software Product Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Data Quality Model. International Standard, 2008.
- [ISO/IEC, 11] ISO/IEC 25040: Systems and Software Engineering – Evaluation Process. International Standard, 2011.
- [ISO/IEC, 15] ISO/IEC 25024: Systems and Software Engineering – Measurement of Data Quality. International Standard, 2015.

- [ISO, 16] ISO 8000-61: Data Quality – Part 61: Data Quality Management: Process Reference Model. International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, 2016. <https://www.iso.org/standard/54186.html>
- [Kitchenham, 95] Kitchenham, B. A., Pickard, L. M., Pfleeger, S. L. Case Studies for Method and Tool Evaluation. *IEEE Software*, 12(4), 52–62, 1995.
- [Krishnan, 16] Krishnan, S., Franklin, M. J., Goldberg, K., Wang, J., Wu, E. ActiveClean: Interactive Data Cleaning for Machine Learning. In: *SIGMOD 2016*, 2117–2120.
- [Ladley, 12] J. Data Governance: How to Design, Deploy and Sustain an Effective Data Governance Program. Morgan Kaufmann, Waltham, MA, 2012.
- [Laney, 17] Laney, D. B. *Infonomics: How to Monetize, Manage, and Measure Information as an Asset for Competitive Advantage*. Routledge, New York, NY, 2017.
- [Loshin, 13] Loshin, D. *Big Data Analytics: From Strategic Planning to Enterprise Integration with Tools, Techniques, NoSQL, and Graph*. Elsevier (Morgan Kaufmann), Waltham, MA, 2013.
- [Mahanti, 19] Mahanti, R. *Data Quality: Dimensions, Measurement, Strategy, Management, and Governance*. ASQ Quality Press, Milwaukee, WI, 2019.
- [Makary, 16] Makary, M. A., Daniel, M. Medical error—the third leading cause of death in the US. *BMJ*, 353, i2139, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i2139>
- [Mangipudi, 21] Mangipudi, M. R., Prasad, K., Vaidya, R. W. Objectives and Key Results for Higher Educational Institutions. *Pacific Business Review International*, 2021.
- [Niven, 16] Niven, P. R., Lamorte, B. *Objectives and Key Results: Driving Focus, Alignment, and Engagement with OKRs*. Wiley, 2016.
- [Olson, 03] Olson, J. E. *Data Quality: The Accuracy Dimension*. Morgan Kaufmann (Elsevier), San Francisco, CA, 2003.
- [Raman, 01] Raman, V., Hellerstein, J. M. Potter’s Wheel: An Interactive Data Cleaning System. In: *VLDB 2001*, 381–390.
- [Rahm, 00] Rahm, E., Do, H. H. Data Cleaning: Problems and Current Approaches. *IEEE Data Engineering Bulletin*, 23(4), 3–13, 2000.
- [Redman, 97] Redman, T. C. *Data Quality for the Information Age*. Artech House, Norwood, MA, 1997.
- [Redman, 98] Redman, T. C. The Impact of Poor Data Quality on the Typical Enterprise. *Communications of the ACM*, 41(2), 79–82, 1998. <https://doi.org/10.1145/269012.269025>
- [Redman, 08] Redman, T. C. *Data Driven: Profiting from Your Most Important Business Asset*. Harvard Business Review Press, Boston, MA, 2008.
- [Redman, 16] Redman, T. C. Bad Data Costs the U.S. 3 Trillion Per Year. *Harvard Business Review*, September 2016.
- [Rekatsinas, 17] Rekatsinas, T., Chu, X., Ilyas, I. F., Ré, C. HoloClean: Holistic Data Repairs. *PVLDB*, 10(11), 1190–1201, 2017.
- [Robson, 02] Robson, C. *Real World Research: A Resource for Social Scientists and Practitioner-Researchers*. 2nd ed., Blackwell, 2002.
- [Sherman, 14] Sherman, R. *Business Intelligence Guidebook: From Data Integration to Analytics*. Morgan Kaufmann (Elsevier), Burlington, MA, 2014.

- [Sowkasem, 21] Sowkasem, C., Kirawanich, P. A Deliverable Delay Management of Software Development in Railway Project using an OKR-Based Scrum Process. In: Proceedings of ICSIM 2021, 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3451471.3451473>
- [Taylor, 22] Taylor, P. Volume of data/information created, captured, copied, and consumed worldwide. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/871513/worldwide-data-created/>, 2022.
- [Troian, 22] Troian, A., Prado, E., Reinehr, S., Malucelli, A. OKRs as a Results-Focused Management Model: A Systematic Literature Review. In: Proceedings of IHC 2022. ACM, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3554360.3558473>
- [UNE, 23] UNE 0077: Data Governance; UNE 0078: Data Management; UNE 0079: Data Quality Management. Asociación Española de Normalización (UNE), Madrid, 2023.
- [Verdugo, 20] Verdugo, J., Rodríguez, M. Assessing data cybersecurity using ISO/IEC 25012. *Software Quality Journal*, 28, 965–985. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11219-019-09494-x>, 2020.
- [Verdugo, 24] Verdugo, J., Oviedo, J., Rodríguez, M., Piattini, M. Connecting Research and Practice for Software Product Quality Evaluation and Certification: A Software Laboratory’s 25-Year Journey. *IEEE Software*, 41(3), 33–40, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2024.3357119>
- [Wibawa, 21] Wibawa, A. S., Budiardjo, E. K., Mahatma, K. Improving the Quality of Requirements Engineering Process in Software Development with Agile Methods: A Case Study Telemedicine Startup XYZ. In: Proceedings of ICADEIS 2021, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICADEIS52521.2021.9701962>
- [Wohlin, 12] Wohlin, C., Runeson, P., Höst, M., Ohlsson, M. C., Regnell, B., Wesslén, A. *Experimentation in Software Engineering*. Springer, 2012.
- [Yakaout, 11] Yakout, M., Elmagarmid, A. K., Neville, J., Ouzzani, M., Ilyas, I. F. Guided Data Repair. *PVLDB*, 4(5), 279–289, 2011.
- [Yakaout, 13] Yakout, M., Berti-Équille, L., Elmagarmid, A. K. Scalable Automatic Repairing. In: *SIGMOD 2013*, 553–564.
- [Yin, 09] Yin, R. K. *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 4th ed., Sage Publications, 2009.